

COLLATERAL DAMAGES FROM NIGERIA'S NORTH-EAST

VOICES OF THE MENTALLY-AFFLICTED

**CHUKWUEMEKA EMMANUEL-DIO
MARY ONMA EMMANUEL**

Texto Aberto Série II - n.º 2 | 2023 (ISSN: 2184-2388)

ABSTRACT

Nigeria is best described as a country under siege. Almost every geo-political region in its territory has in the past ten years been characterized by one or multiple typologies of violent conflict, most of them happening simultaneously. Often accompanying these conflicts are attendant health challenges, many of which remain vaguely or under-reported. From a public health perspective, this paper explores the Boko Haram insurgency in North-East Nigeria. In examining the mental health problems affecting Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs), it also puts the spotlight on the link between human rights violations and Combat Stress Reaction (CSR) among security operatives, a perspective hardly taken into account in cognate literature. Data from interviews, focus groups and secondary sources were used to support the postulations of this paper. Major findings reveal that incidents of abductions, targeted killings, and sexual abuse have resulted in severe cases of PTSD among IDPs, while the military contend mostly with occupational hazards and deplorable working conditions.

Projections from this study point to elevated health security threat levels for the region should less priority be given to the provision of commensurate, psycho-social support for all the actors in the theater of armed conflict. Projections from this study point to elevated health security threat levels for the region should less priority be given to the provision of commensurate, psycho-social support for all the actors in the theater of armed conflict.

KEYWORDS

Conflict, Boko Haram, Mental Health, Human Rights, Nigeria.

Chukwuemeka Emmanuel-Dio, is a Research Fellow with the French Institute for Research in Africa (IFRA), University of Ibadan, Nigeria; Email: mekmanuels@gmail.com

Mary Onma Emmanuel, is a Public Health Officer and Graduate Student at the Department of Community Medicine, University of Jos, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Adamawa, Borno, and Yobe States have been the epicenter of a jihadist insurgency in Nigeria's North-East region. Since the inception of its violent phase in 2009, the Boko Haram insurgency has left in its wake, an unparalleled loss of lives and the destruction of property never recorded in the country's history of violent conflicts. Latest statistics in 2020 show that over 27,000 people have been killed in the insurgency, while 3 million persons were displaced.[1] Other reports display significant discrepancies in fatality rates with 53,000 deaths – cumulative of combat and terrorism related deaths,[2] and 3 million internally displaced.[3] It is indeed a worrisome humanitarian nightmare, as it depicts a sharp increase from the 20,000 killed and 2,000,000 internally displaced persons earlier reported in 2017.[4]

Boko Haram's actual history can be traced back to 2003 in Kanama, a village located in the North Eastern State of Yobe. Under its then militant leader, Mohammed Ali, the group engaged in violent confrontations with the Nigerian military, leading to the decimation of the group members, with its remnants mobilizing to join a new leader – the charismatic Ustaz Mohammed Yusuf, in Borno

State.[5] The Saudi-trained Yusuf who took over the leadership of the group from 2005 was actively involved in the fiery proselytization of his infamous doctrines that fundamentally opposed the western value system, eventually earning the group its popular name, “Boko Haram” meaning – Western education is forbidden. As a testament to its ideological objective, the group is also known as – *Jama'atu Ahlis Sunna Lidda'awati Wal-Jihad* (people committed to the propagation of the Prophet's teachings and jihad).[6] Boko Haram's eventual adoption of violence as a tool for proselytization was not spontaneous as this could be blamed on a constellation of factors, explored in the next section.

THE BOKO HARAM INSURGENCY – CAUSALITIES

Scholars of religious fundamentalism and violent extremism vis a viz Boko Haram have discerned a three-layered causal factor of the insurgency. Insights from Mbaezue point to poverty, unemployment and the lack of formal education among the local populace in Borno State as central to the root factors that led to the emergence of the group.[7] However these conditions as argued and further explained in Usman and Afonne are in actual sense,

[1] International Committee on Nigeria (ICON) and International Organisation for Peacebuilding and Social Justice (PSJ). *Nigeria's Silent Slaughter: Genocide in Nigeria and the Implications for the International Community* (Washington: International Committee on Nigeria and International Organization for Peace building and Social Justice, 2020).

[2] J. Warner and H. Matfess, *Exploding Stereotypes: The Unexpected Operational and Demographic Characteristics of Boko Haram's Suicide Bombers* (West Point: Combating Terrorism Centre United States Military Academy, 2017).

[3] Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre and Norwegian Refugee Council, “Global Report on Internal Displacement 2019” (June 10, 2020), <https://www.internal-displacement.org/global-report/grid2019/>.

[4] M. Aimee-Noel, *How Boko Haram Specifically Targets Displaced People* (Addis Ababa: Institute for Security Studies, 2017).

[5] M. Kyari, “The Message and Methods of Boko Haram,” In M. Pérouse de Montclos, (ed), *Boko Haram, Islamism, Politics, Security and the State in Nigeria* (Ibadan: African Studies Centre, 2014).

[6] E. Mbaezue, “Revisiting Boko Haram: The Unheeded Early Warning Signs,” *Spoor* (July 28, 2021), <https://medium.com/spoor-africa/early-warning-signals-and-conflict-prevention-examining-the-rise-of-the-boko-haram-insurgency-in-f956eb56dab4>.

[7] Mbaezue (See note 6).

artificial conditions created by the political elites of Northern Nigeria, to remain socio-politically relevant and in the corridors of power.[8] [9] They are structural defects that have been deliberately entrenched among the local populace, and designed in such a way that the lower class can neither resist nor revolt, remaining perpetually subservient to the so-called ruling class.

At the proximate level of causal factors of the insurgency is predominately the influence of the foreign actors. Filiu and Morgan are quick to correlate the activities of the group in the early days of the post-2009 violent era of its operations, with the sponsorship and training they received from their North and East African counterparts - Algeria, Libya, and Somalia.[10] [11] Hence the influence of regional actors such as Algeria's Salafist Group for Preaching and Combat (GSPC), Islamic State in Libya, and Somalia's Al Shabaab in East Africa, escalated the intensity of Boko Haram's insurgency in Nigeria's North East, while the influx of weapons and foreign fighters from across the border remain irrefutable proofs of this regional alliance - an alliance determined to paralyze every form of Western influence in the region. Those regional actors in Africa were in turn united in their quest by the ideologies of Al Qaeda, and the Islamic State in Iraq and Syria (ISIS).[12] [13]

The triggers leading to the insurgency's violent phase are dominant in existing literature. Mbaezue in retracing the chain of events that happened in 2009 identifies the extra-judicial

killing of the sect's members as one of such immediate causes.[14] It began with a special team of police officers known as "operation flush", firing live rounds of ammunition on Mohammed Yusuf's sect for refusing to wear crash helmets during a burial procession. This led to violent reactions and counter-reactions from both the group and security operatives, culminating in the arrest and extra-judicial killings of Mohammed Yusuf and his men, ultimately heralding the violent phase of the insurgency that has spanned for over a decade. [15]

Expectedly, a region that has been engulfed in such protracted violent conflict is bound to be characterized by grave health challenges experienced by all the actors in its theater of operations. While this study explores how the exposure to different degrees of trauma has aggravated the mental health challenges faced by IDPs, it also acknowledges the quintessential need to identify the markings and possible implications of those same health conditions on the conduct of security personnel deployed to the region. As an integral component of the same environment, the extent of the security personnel's inclusion in efforts seeking to address the health recovery needs of civilians remains a key determinant of success, and the sustainability of response mechanisms targeting holistic wellness for all the afflicted.

[8] Y. Usman, "Reasons behind the Emergence of Boko Haram," *Compass* (December 5, 2012), <http://www.compassnewspaper.org>

[9] E. Afonne, "Ministry of Northern Nigeria: Wrong pill for the Ailing North," *Nigerian Newsworld*, (April 30, 2012).

[10] P. Filiu, *Al-Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb: Algerian Challenge or Global Threat?* (Middle East Program: Carnegie Paper, 2009).

[11] A. Morgan, "Al Qaeda's North African connection," *Familysecuritymatters.org* (May 10, 2009), http://www.familysecuritymatters.org/publications/id.4525/pub_detail.asp.

[12] A. Agbo, "Bin Laden's Men in Nigeria," *Tell* (May 16, 2011).

[13] R. Mauro, *Boko Haram: Nigerian Islamist group* (The Clarion Project: Special Report, 2015).

[14] Mbaezue (see note 6)

[15] Agbo (See note 12)

MENTAL HEALTH DISORDER: PERSPECTIVES FROM INTERNALLY DISPLACED PERSONS (IDPS)

As victims of violent conflict, Internally Displaced Persons are susceptible to a wide range of sicknesses. When categorized, such ailments could be emotional, physiological, and psychological. Due to the physical manifestation and ubiquitous nature of ailments such as malaria, typhoid, acute respiratory infections, sexually transmitted diseases, and malnutrition, it is not uncommon for individuals to attach more importance, and with it, lethality, to this category of illnesses. However, such prioritizing which is mostly an outcome of societal perception is quite detached from actuality. Health conditions like depression, anxiety disorders, panic disorders, suicidal tendencies, and other forms of post-traumatic stress disorders share the same mortality rates if not more with the physiological ailments. They are commensurately malignant owing to their capacity to impede or completely hamper a person's ability to function optimally. It is in a bid to publicly sensitize on the dangers posed by these psycho-social threats to wellness that the International Community began drawing global attention to the challenges of mental health disorder faced by Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs). Weighing in on this emerging discourse, scholars affirm that governments and humanitarian agencies so far have prioritized the physical health needs of IDPs, paying less, or sometimes, no attention to their

mental health challenges.[16] For other studies, the needs of asylum seekers and refugees have enjoyed preferential treatment compared to that of internally displaced persons.[17]

Perhaps the clinical and non-clinical complexities involved in the detection and treatment of psychosocial problems among IDPs may be informing the category of needs that stakeholders prioritize for intervention. Also to be taken into account is the likelihood of humanitarian actors getting motivated by the glitz associated with the public view of their overt show of affection to the internally displaced. Further is the near obsession with the project interests of donors (sometimes incompatible with the needs on ground) – steadily informing the choice of industry players to focus on the provision of relief materials, neglecting other core needs of the survivors of violent conflict. Regardless of the rationale driving interventions, it is sacrosanct that for best results, a needs-based, context specific approach must be integrated in humanitarian interventions targeting internally displaced persons. Although relief materials provide quick fixes to some of the stressors that traumatize IDPs, they lack depth and are hardly sustainable. These measures can do very little in the face of the literal nightmares and flashbacks that are permanently lodged in the psychic of people displaced by violent conflicts. The situation calls for a robust strategy featuring a complimentary, symbiotic, inter-dependent relationship where the access to relief materials must be accompanied with the provision of mental health and psycho-social support for victims.

[16] B. Kaiser, C. Ticao, J. Boglosa, et al., "A. Mental Health and Psychosocial Support Needs Among People Displaced by Boko Haram in Nigeria," *Global Public Health* 15/3 (2020).

[17] D. Miliband and M. Tessema, "The Unmet Needs of Refugees and Internally Displaced People," *Lancet* 392/10164 (2022).

Mental health in conceptual terms has a connotation that extends beyond the absence of mental disabilities or disorders. [18] It is safer to perceive mental health in more holistic terms – the totality of one’s physical, emotional, and mental well-being. Extant studies analyzing the nexus between mental health and internal displacement in Ethiopia, Nigeria and Somalia reveal that a total of 14.4 million IDPs from the above countries are suffering from depression and PTSDs.[19] The report further elaborates that usually 30% of internally displaced persons end up with a mental health problem.[20] Meanwhile, an estimated figure on the prevalence of mental health problems among non-displaced populations in the world is put at 3.4% which in comparative terms to that of the global IDP population, is far less.[21]

Among the Nigerian population, the rate of mental health disorder has been put between 12% - 26%, translating to 20 million people being at risk of experiencing one form of mental health problem or the other in their life time.[22] Concerning its IDP population, further statistics by the World Health Organisation shows that 1 in 5 displaced persons comes down with mental health issues,[23] connoting that presently, an estimated 400,000 IDPs in Borno State are suffering from mental health problems. Disabled persons, and mostly children, and youths are most affected thus corroborating

an earlier study of IDPs conducted in Columbia where the results also showed that displaced teenagers are the worst hit by mental health problems as they tend to come down with suicidal tendencies ranging from thoughts to attempts[24]. The fore-going presents no other intellectual outcome to scholars but what is already opined – that Internally Displaced Persons from the jihadist insurgency in North-East Nigeria present an ideal study group for PTSD among IDPs because the threats of mental health problems they present could serve as a prototype for understanding similar cases among victims of violent conflict in sub-Saharan Africa,[25] making it a humanitarian silver-lining for the region.

Narratives from health workers and mental health experts deployed to the deep fields of Borno State depict further insights on this regional emergency that is bedeviling the entire North-East. Beginning with the view of a field officer from UNICEF – Phuong Nguyen, the children in Borno, and the North-East are paying a steep price for a violent conflict they know nothing about its beginning. The psychological trauma most of the children end up with is an outcome of their steady exposure to violence, in addition to other risk factors such as discrimination, stigmatization, social isolation, and the displacement itself. Early detection is key to containing this mental health condition, Nguyen concludes.[26]

[18] M. White, F. Adam, and T. Rachel, “What is Mental Health?” (December 22, 2022), <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/154543#treatment>

[19] Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre (IDMC), “Key Findings on Internal Displacement and Mental Health” (October 5, 2021), <https://www.internal-displacement.org/expert-opinion/5-key-findings-on-internal-displacement-and-mental-health>.

[20] Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre (IDMC) (See note 19)

[21] IDMC (see note 19)

[22] IDMC (see note 19)

[23] O. Gureje, V. Lasebikan, L. Kola, and V. Makanjuola, “Life-time and 12-Month Prevalence of Mental Disorders in the Nigerian survey of Public Mental Health and Well-Being,” *British Journal of Psychiatry* 5/7 (2018).

[24] Gureje et al. (see note 23)

[25] N. Musa, “Refugee Crises in Nigeria, Cameroon, Eight Others, World’s most Neglected,” (June 10, 2020), <https://guardian.ng/news/refugee-crises-in-nigeria-cameroon-eight-others-worlds-mostneglected/>.

[26] D. Tolu-Kolawale, “How North-East Children Battling Mental Health Trauma of Boko Haram War Find Solace in Rehabilitation Home,” *Punch* (January, 08, 2022), <https://punchng.com/how-north-east-children-battling-mental-health-trauma-of-boko-haram-war-find-solace-in-rehabilitation-home/>.

Boniface Owoicho, a mental health officer, similarly expresses worry over the fate of Borno's children. According to him, the violence and serial abductions perpetuated by Boko Haram against children, has resulted in the psychological and social well-being of these children being mortally damaged.[27] Many of them begin to suffer different forms of depression and PTSD which Adebayo notes could relapse into another circle of violence. [28]

The children themselves being the direct victims of this surge in violence have even more graphic ordeals to share. Amina, a youth, and internally displaced female in Borno could not withhold her emotions as she shared her experience over the kidnapping of her school teacher and friends by Boko Haram. According to her, "I cried for days, could not eat, and frustrated, my eyes turned red, and my throat got dried".[29] In the case of Yakubu, a male who witnessed the gruesome killing of his grandmother beheaded before his eyes, "I had never seen someone killed with a sword in my life before my grandmother was beheaded with a sword by Boko Haram...I fell into a coma and later was revived, I cried, sobered and refused to eat and talk to people for two days".[30] Further on the subject, most of the children experienced such high levels of psycho-social withdrawal that they began struggling with their academic activities.[31] Their former

learning environments which used to be a sanctuary for them now became a constant reminder of the terror they witnessed seeing their teachers and friends, kidnapped and in extreme cases killed. For the children who were able to overcome the trauma and remain in school, poor academic performance became their new challenge. Fear and the recurring flashbacks of the horror meted on them by Boko Haram continued to impede their performance, compelling many of them to withdraw from school.[32] Qouta, Punamaki and El Sarraj explain these psycho-social ramifications, stating that children exposed to protracted killings and murders have an increased likelihood of developing low cognitive abilities and problem focusing.[33]

From Gworza Local Government of Borno State come more harrowing tales, this time from traumatized adolescent victims of sexual abuse in IDP Camps:

I was married to a Boko Haram fighter in the bush before I left him to reside on my own, no husband to protect and support me. When I was harassed and raped by personnel of the Civilian Joint Task Force (CJTF), I was helpless; there was nothing I could do except go to the hospital and take some medication....why is the CJTF doing this to us? The memories are so painful and I don't wish to remember the events of that night.[34]

[27] Tolu-Kolawale (see note 26)

[28] A. Adeboye, "Addressing the Boko Haram-Induced Mental Health Burden in Nigeria," *Health and Human Rights Journal*, 23/1 (2021).

[29] P. Adepelumi, *Psychological Consequences of the Boko Haram Insurgency for Nigerian Children*, PhD thesis (Walden University, 2018), p.124.

[30] Adepelumi (See note 29)

[31] Adepelumi (See note 29)

[32] Adepelumi (See note 29)

[33] S. Qouta, R. Punamäki, E. Montgomery, and E. El Sarraj, "Predictors of Psychological Distress and Positive Resources among Palestinian Adolescents: Trauma, Child, and Mothering Characteristics," *Child Abuse and Neglect* 7/12 (2007).

[34] Key Informant Interview with survivor 1 from Camp C, Pulka - Gworza Local Government, Borno State, December 10, 2019.

The experience was far worse for the next victim whose testimony beyond corroborating the horrific tales from the IDP camps, makes further startling revelations on the complicity of security personnel in acts of sexual abuse against young internally displaced females:

On one fateful night at around 10pm, some personnel of the Civilian Joint Task Force, almost 25 in number, visited us while we slept. They tried stealing from us, they beat us. Then some of them began arguing among themselves on whether they should rape me or not. Eventually they did, after threatening me with weapons. After I was raped, I went to the hospital for medical check-up, and then subsequently reported the case to LHI. My brother took the issue to the camp manager, and he did nothing about it. I don't know the imam here; had it been it was before when I was a Christian, I would have gone to my pastor. Right now am in a dilemma...in my opinion this happened to me because there were no military personnel in the camp, this is how the CJTF keep harassing us all the time...my chest still hurts as a result of the beatings I got that day...[35]

Contrary to her view that the presence of soldiers would have deterred the sexual abuse young females suffer from members of the state vigilante service, a community elder recounts an ordeal in a neighboring community that implicates some the soldiers deployed to that area:

Harassment and assaulting of women in the community is common because even last year, a soldier collected someone's wife and beat up the husband to the extent of wounding the man. I went to the bulama to report the incident who in turn took a corrective measure by referring the case to the Commanding Officer of the solders, who called the solder to order. The Commanding Officer also encouraged us to report other similar cases to him if any arises.[36]

[35] Key Informant Interview with survivor 2 from Camp C, Pulka - Gworza Local Government, Borno State, December 10, 2019.

[36] Key Informant Interview with a community elder from Zariaga, community in Gworza Local Government, December 11, 2019.

[37] Focus Group Discussion conducted for men at VI community, Michika Local Government, Adamawa State, December 13, 2019.

[38] E. Abiama, C. Ifeagwazi, and C. JohnBosco, "Rates of Occurrence and Influence of Trauma Exposure on Posttraumatic Stress Disorder Symptoms among Survivors of Terrorist Attacks in Northeast Nigeria," *International Journal of Mental Health and Addiction* 10/1007 (2021).

From Adamawa, the neighboring State directly bordering Borno, male respondents in a focus group discussion similarly accused the military of sexually abusing and seducing their women which in most cases has led to matrimonial conflicts in many homes. According to one of the respondents:

They harass our girls sexually and later impregnate them, making their lives miserable; not only the girls but also our wives...we want their checkpoints to be moved far from this area into the bush because they seduce our women with money and other material things, making them stubborn whenever we talk to them.[37]

Such relational conflicts often deteriorate to broken homes, leaving the women and children more traumatized in the face of an already tense, soaring humanitarian situation.

The nexus between violent conflict, mental health problems and human right violations is uncontested. Human right violations which tend to characterize most armed conflicts are build-ups to psychologically unstable environments where vulnerable persons become less protected and feel less safe. The end-result of these hostile settings are psychologically damaging to individuals, many of who never recover from different forms of PTSD, owing to their exposure to various degrees of trauma, as rigorously explored and validated in Abiama, Ifeagwazi, and Chukwuorji.[38] Another perspective to this discourse however is the psychological state of the perpetrators of rights violations themselves. The next section attempts to establish the connection between human rights violations and Combat Stress Reaction

(CSR), a debilitating mental health condition that affects military personnel actively serving in war zones. The objective is to investigate, and possibly draw logical conclusions on whether or not the human rights violations of civilians in conflict zones, are in most cases as both unintended and intentional as they are inevitable, and whether the effects could be avoided or mitigated.

HUMAN RIGHTS AND CIVIL-MILITARY RELATIONS IN NIGERIA'S NORTH-EAST

Nigeria is no stranger to human rights violations. Its infamous days of the military interregnum may have bequeathed to generations, a distasteful “culture” where the dignity of human existence is merely a lofty idea, even with the constitutional provisions meant to protect such in place. The situation has left a systemic rot that cascades from the leadership, down to the commoner. It is no surprise therefore, having these different shades of “new-normal” as regards human rights violations currently operating in the country: -
 - fragrant disregard for court rulings; assault on civilians by security operatives; restriction of certain key liberties (protests, strikes, freedom of speech); government-sanctioned murder; interference with the affairs of the

judiciary by the executive; extra-judicial killings; wide-scale corruption and cover-ups at the highest levels of government with resulting effects at the lowest levels of the society where the quality of living has worsened. Nigeria's history of human rights violation, though with a mostly local coloration also come with far-reaching, disturbing international consequences. This in part is due to how those grave human rights violations on the domestic front tend to affect regional peace and security in West Africa where the country is perceived to be the guiding light and beacon of hope for many. Worse still, as a signatory to several treaties, key among them, the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the Country's failure to show commitment in upholding these globally-approved principles of healthy co-existence, makes Her morally culpable on all fronts.

The only dynamics to the human rights situation in Nigeria, as some would opine, is the emergence of non-state actors led by Boko Haram, in the perpetuation of human rights abuses.[39] Aligning with this position, this paper argues that Boko Haram as a non-state actor is only replicating a norm from the playbook of the Nigerian government when it comes to the welfare of its citizens. They have been the silent observers for many years, and so can now conveniently match the government, strategy for strategy in the context of rights violations. Reports from

[39] B. Abiri, and B. Maigari, *Human Rights Violations in Nigeria* (Lagos-Nigeria: Cleen Foundation, 2014).

Amnesty International, Human Rights Watch, including first-hand accounts from interviews conducted among IDPs and host communities in the North-East all contain a flurry of narratives blaming soldiers of the Nigerian military for gross human rights abuses of the civilian population. The aim of this paper is not to further pursue this line of argument; instead it presents an alternate perspective, one that depicts the security operatives themselves as victims of the same insurgency they are fighting.

MENTAL HEALTH DISORDER: A MILITARY STANDPOINT

The effects of war on the soldier are not only physical; they are accompanied by less visible, but deeply scathing psychological throes. The sights and sounds of war where both friends and foes are slaughtered on a massive scale usually leave many of the surviving soldiers with indelible horrific imprimaturs. Although from the perspective of military psychology, Solomon opines that battlefield tension and stress are useful environmental conditions that stimulate the much-needed vigilance required for optimum performance in the battlefield, they are not without dire consequences which he identifies as Combat Stress Reaction (CSR). [40] CSR is a health condition, a state of psychological paralysis whereby soldiers exhibit an uncontrollable, intense, and often prolonged sense of vulnerability, resulting in their inability to distance themselves from

perceived overwhelming threats that often result in total behavioral distortions, making them unfit for duty.[41] It is that inevitable fall-out of war, a personal loss but with dire cost to an army.

The symptoms of Combat Stress Reaction vary, and have been broadly classified into three; - psychosomatic, cognitive, and emotional symptoms.[42] The psychosomatic signs include; fatigue, vomiting, stuttering, paralysis, and loss of bowel control. The cognitive symptoms are mostly cerebral in nature and are believed to manifest in the following terms; confusion, disorientation, war neurosis, and difficulty making the right judgment. The last category of symptoms operate at the emotional level but with very strong connections to behavioral tendencies that could result in violence, among them; paralyzing anxiety, deep depression, shell shock, and fierce agitation.

Combat Stress Reaction (CSR) has been strongly linked to, or is more or less, perceived to be one of the earliest stages of Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD).[43] This is considering that individuals who suffer from CSR tend to eventually come down with PTSD co-morbidity. Using the concepts of secondary traumatization and vicarious victimization, Solomon proceeds to explain how persons in close proximity to soldiers with CSR, end up traumatized themselves. He blames it on mostly the behavioral exhibitions of the traumatized soldiers, many of who become withdrawn, edgy, and in extreme cases, uncontrollably aggressive and enraged, the

[40] Z. Solomon, "The Impact of Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder in Military Situations," *Journal of Clinical Psychiatry* 62/ 15 (2001).

[41] Solomon (see note 40)

[42] Z. Solomon, "Psychological Sequelae of War: A 3-Year Prospective Study of Israeli Combat Stress Reaction Casualties," *Journal of Nervous Mental Disorder* 177/15 (1989).

[43] Z. Solomon, Y. Neria, A. Ohry, "PTSD among Israeli Former Prisoners of War and Soldiers with Combat Stress Reaction: A Longitudinal Study," *American Journal of Psychiatry* 8/151 (1994).

outcome which could be violent, or abuse of an emotional nature.[44] According to a soldier, “let me just tell you, the environment alone, if you are not careful, it affects one’s psychic. That is just the truth. That is why some of us end up having psychological problems.”[45]

Insider perspectives from data collected on this subject further consolidate many of the submissions vigorously researched by experts on the discourse. The findings appear to be compelling a change in the popular narrative that predominately depicts soldiers and other security personnel as villains. Apparently, what many have come to see as human rights abuses on the part of soldiers, are in actual sense, different forms of psycho-social vulnerabilities, masking as unchecked aggression and delinquencies.

The soldier’s account of events in the field most times constitutes what is termed, “the untold story”. Constrained by military codes of conduct which prohibit the unauthorized disclosure of information by serving personnel, many soldiers of the Nigerian Army have imbibed the culture of silence when it comes to sharing the experiences connected with the professional hazards that typically define their jobs, further complicated by the peculiar nature of their deplorable conditions of service that catalyze the violation of their own rights as soldiers. The end-results of such violations are almost inevitable, if not predictable. A soldier who dared share his story but on the strictest condition of anonymity, had this to say:

I was deployed from one of the States in the North-central, to Bama in 2013 when the fighting was very hot in Borno. Boko Haram had captured Bama and hoisted their flag, declaring it their territory. For months in the thick forests, my colleagues and I engaged the enemy in fierce battles. We had nothing to eat for days, little ammunition to fight, no warm clothing to shield us from the bitter cold at night. Yet, our superiors who were well-aware of our conditions still ordered us to steadily engage the enemy. A lot of us were killed. I still have problems sleeping at night, I seem to hear the sound of bullets whizzing past my ears like I was still in the trenches. While we were in the fields dying, our commanders were feasting and living large at Pinnacle Hotel in Maiduguri. Sometimes you’re not even paid your salary, or your CO for no reason could withhold your salary, or you get half-pay. Which gallant officer will be happy with this?[46]

Another soldier listening to the interview eagerly contributed:

One thing I first noticed when we got here is that the people don’t like us. Though we came to help them, they see us as the enemy, they see us as invaders, and some of them are willing informants to Boko Haram fighters. They tell the insurgents our locations, and then we get ambushed, and many of us get killed. Most times we don’t even know who our real enemies are; the boko haram fighters, or the civilians we came here to protect? The real number of soldiers killed as a result of the activities of these spies is never disclosed but they are many. Some of these small girls you see here are wives to Boko Haram fighters. Many of us have become suspicious of everybody, and we have developed anxiety. Now we go for anyone we suspect. We all want to leave here alive. Ask me when last I was allowed to travel and see my family. I left my wife two days after our

[44] Z. Solomon, M. Waysman, and G. Levy, “From the Frontline to the Home-Front: A Study of Secondary Traumatization,” *Family Process*, 31 (1992).

[45] Key Informant Interview conducted with soldier 1 at Munguno Local Government, Borno State, April 15, 2020.

[46] Key Informant Interview conducted with soldier 1 at Gworza Local Government, Borno State, December 11, 2019.

wedding. Some of us have been here for three years, others have stayed longer. The sounds of guns and bombs are our only steady companion.[47]

Regardless of these emotive positions, the need to uphold the human rights of civilians caught-up in armed conflict is not totally lost on all the soldiers. Affirming the tenets of healthy civil-military relations, a good number of serving personnel still believe those principles to be sacrosanct, and its observance at the heart of what becomes of many of them even at the end of their military career. As one of the soldiers succinctly attests:

There is one common saying, 'there is life after military work'. Once we retire, we just have to go back to our parents, we go back to them. Our mothers, our sisters are all civilians. Bearing this in mind, we try to maintain that kind of relationship here. When we are given our pass, it is still these same civilians we travel to see.[48]

Similarly, another soldier concurs:

Of course, it is not an option to maintain good relations with the locals. And whatever is not an option, we just have to do it. They need us, we need them. As a matter of fact, we need them a lot more in a way. Why do I say so? Because they are our only contact with the outside world. They have farms in the outskirts of the town, they go to fetch firewood. In the course of these activities, they get information which they share with us, most importantly information on the activities of Boko Haram. They transmit this information at the first entrance of any of the Monguno towns. Besides my professional experience, personally I have also benefitted from good relations with the locals. This is a place where everybody is watching you. They are observing your attitude. You just have to be careful, and respect

yourself. When you respect yourself, you will even see some the locals offer to pay for your goods when you go to the market. In some shops, they will even give you those commodities for free.....[49]

While the engagements in this section of the paper are in no way intended to justify human rights violations by soldiers, the data investigating the occurrences of these violations cannot be overlooked. They harbor prospects for understanding and mitigating further occurrences of those violations which evidently do not occur in isolation (whether intended or unintended). Since empirical evidence so far suggests that no actor in Nigeria's theatre of armed conflict in the North-East is insulated from the mental health challenges that go with residing in that region, a logical assumption therefore would be that most of the residents in the North-East are in dire need of psycho-social support, which could be administered on either preventive or curative basis, side by side the routine relief items.

CONCLUSION

The psycho-social effects of violent conflicts on civilians (IDPs) and security personnel, remains an on-going conversation, and will continue so long as humans are naturally pre-disposed to violent behavior and outcomes. Already, there are trending emerging stories of stuck-on love syndrome between female abductees and their Boko Haram abductors; these remain incontrovertible evidence of the existence, and threat levels of mental health problems the North-East region is facing both actively and passively. Further investigation is

[47] Key Informant Interview conducted with soldier 2 at Gworza Local Government, Borno State, December 11, 2019.

[48] Key Informant Interview conducted with soldier 1 at Monguno Local Government, Borno State, April 15, 2020.

[49] Key Informant Interview conducted with soldier 2 at Monguno Local Government, Borno State, April 15, 2020.

also likely to reveal more typology of mental health cases in the offing. Addressing this developing public health situation which significantly doubles as a clog on the wheels of the basic fundamental human right to healthy living requires intervention strategies that must be preventive and psycho-socially orientated. It begins with robust public sensitization programs that ultimately encourage a culture of speaking-out among the populace. This should be complimented by synergized collaborative efforts among critical stakeholders in the health, humanitarian and development sectors at the state and federal levels of government. Only such collective efforts can provide soothing relief to the afflicted voices of internally displaced persons, and the different security outfits in Nigeria's North-East.

[47] Key Informant Interview conducted with soldier 2 at Gworza Local Government, Borno State, December 11, 2019.

[48] Key Informant Interview conducted with soldier 1 at Monguno Local Government, Borno State, April 15, 2020.

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Coordenador: Joaquim Braga

Coordenadores de edição: Bernardo Ferro, José Beato

Assistentes de edição: Fernando Santor e João Emanuel Diogo

Como citar este texto: Emmanuel-Dio, Chukwuemeka - Emmanuel, Mary Onma, “Collateral Damages from Nigeria’s North-East: Voices of the Mentally-Afflicted”, *Texto Aberto IEF Série II - 02* (2023), pp. 1-10.